

TEMPORAL VARIATION IN ARRIVAL AND PRICES OF ONION IN MAJOR MARKETS OF INDIA.

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Abstract

The present study was an attempt to examine the behaviors of arrival and prices of onion in major markets of India over the period from 2012 to 2022. The entire investigation relies on data obtained from secondary sources. Data on monthly wholesale prices and arrival of selected market was gathered from Agmark.net, APEDA and National Horticultural Board (NHB) Government of India. Five markets were selected from 3 major onion producing states (Lasalgaon, Pimpalgaon, Pune, Bangalore and Ahmedabad). The data collected were subjected to statistical analysis using different methods like moving average, time series models and correlation analysis. Pimpalgaon shows the highest CGR for both arrivals and prices. Pune and Bangalore have negative CGR for arrivals, indicating a decline, while Lasalgaon and Ahmedabad show positive growth in prices. Notably, there's a general increase in arrival quantities over time with varying price volatility indicated by CV (%), highlighting the dynamic nature of agricultural markets. And for CDI Pimpalgaon showing the highest increase from 47.94 to 61.11. Ahmedabad, despite having the lowest initial value at 19.20, recorded a significant rise to 58.26. The seasonal indices reveal significant fluctuations in both arrivals and prices across all markets. Prices tend to peak from August to November, coinciding with lower arrivals, indicating a typical supply-demand relationship. Conversely, higher arrivals in the early months of the year generally correspond to lower prices. The cyclical indices for onion arrivals and prices in major Indian markets generally show a decreasing trend from 2012 to 2022. Prices exhibit more significant fluctuations compared to arrival quantities, indicating higher volatility. The data suggests that while arrivals maintain a relatively steady pattern, prices are more influenced by external market factors. Correlation analysis revealed varied relationships between arrivals and prices across markets.

Keywords: Onion, Arrival and Prices, Price Behavior, CGR, Variability, Seasonality, Correlation.

Introduction and Objectives

The temporal variation in the arrival and prices of onions in major Indian markets such as Lasalgaon, Pimpalgaon, Pune, Bangalore and Ahmedabad, is a critical area of study due to its significant impact on both producers and consumers. These markets, being key hubs for onion trade, exhibit distinct patterns in terms of supply and pricing influenced by various factors including seasonal production cycles, weather conditions, and market demand. Understanding these variations is essential for developing effective strategies to stabilize prices and ensure a steady supply, thereby benefiting farmers and consumers alike. The study is designed to analyze trends, seasonal fluctuations, inter-annual variations, cyclical indices, and correlations in onion arrivals and prices across these markets, offering insights that could guide policymaking and market interventions.

The trend factor in onion arrivals and prices typically denotes the patterns or shifts over time in both the quantity of onions reaching the markets and their corresponding prices. The Arrival Trend signifies the quantity of onions that are brought to the market. Trend in an arrival can be influenced by various factors such as harvest seasons, weather condition and the supply chain disruptions. For an instance, during the peak harvest season, the arrival of onions in the market is typically higher. As per the researchers the price trend refers to the irregular rising and falling in the prices of onions over time. prices can be generally affected by the supply (arrival), Demand, transportation costs, and other market dynamics. for example, if there is a lower arrival due to some reasons like poor harvest, environmental factors, then price may increase due to reduced supply. Monitoring project trends helps in understanding the market conditions, which can be critical for Farmers, Traders and the consumers in making informed decision

These price fluctuation in agricultural commodities are biggest obstacle in the way of an agricultural development. The knowledge on an inter-relation between the arrival and prices of farm product is required for evaluate the extent of the price fluctuations over time. The formulation of a robust agricultural pricing policy crucially depends on the analysis of commodity arrivals and price trends over time.

Analysing the timing and prices of commodities enables farmers to identify the optimal marketing period for their agricultural products to ensure a higher return. Thus, it helps them to take decision with regards to when to sale so as to obtain maximum price.

The continuous changing prices of an onion has been one of the major factors that affecting the income levels of the Indian farmers. Due to increased agricultural production every year, the arrival in the market was increased and also increases prices along with the time. Normally every year the increasing trend is seen in arrival and prices of agricultural commodities because of the high demand and ecological condition.

The study was undertaken with the following objectives.

- 1) To study the Trend and Variations in Arrival and Prices of Onion.
- 2) To workout Seasonal Indices of Arrival and Prices of Onion.
- 3) To estimate Cyclical Indices of Arrival and Prices of Onion.
- 4) To study the relationship between Arrival and Prices of Onion.

Materials and Methods

The Present study was based only on secondary data. The data was collected From the Government website of www.agmarknet.com and National Horticultural Board (NHB). The data on arrival and prices were Collected from the five major onion Market in India namely Lasalgaon, Pimpalgaon, Pune, Bangalore and Ahmedabad. The data were collected for the period of 10 years from the year of 2012-13 to 2022-23. The Collected data was analyzed by using different analytical technique which are as Follows.

Trend and Variation in Arrival and Prices of Onion**Compound Growth Rate**

In present study the compound growth rates in arrival and prices of onion were estimated as follows.

The exponential equation of the following types is used

$$Y = ab^t$$

Were,

Y=Arrival and Prices

a=Intercept or constant

b= Trend coefficient/Regression.

t= Time variable

Annual compound growth rate in percentage is calculated as.

$$CGR (\%) = [\text{Antilog of } (\text{Log } b) - 1] \times 100$$

Coefficient of variation

Coefficient of variation in prices and arrivals was computed to see the variation and predict the behavior of prices and arrival whether they are stable involving less risk and uncertainty and vice-versa.

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{x}} \times 100$$

Where,
 σ = Standard deviation
 \bar{x} = Arithmetic mean.
Cuddy-Delle Valle instability index
 To check the variability in arrival and prices, coefficient of variation (CV) and Cuddy-Della Valle index (CDVI) was used as follows:
 $CDVI (\%) = CV\sqrt{(1 - R)^2}$
 Where,
 CV=coefficient of variation
 $\sqrt{(1 - R)^2}$ = Adjusted coefficient of multiple determination

Seasonal indices in arrival and prices of onion
 The Seasonal indices of arrival and Prices of an onion was worked out by using the simple moving average method.
 $SI = \frac{\text{Monthly average of arrival and prices} \times 100}{\text{Average of monthly average}}$

Cyclical indices of Arrival and Prices of Onion
 Cyclical indices were calculated for the arrival and prices of onion from the multiplicative model of time series data.
 $\text{Cyclical indices} = \frac{\text{Original yearly value} \times 100}{\text{Estimated trend value}}$
 $= \frac{T \times C \times I}{T} \times 100$
 $= (C \times I) \times 100$

Where,
 T=Trend
 C=Cyclical component

I=Irregular component

Correlation between Arrival and Prices

The correlation is the measure of degree of relationship amongst two series i.e. Arrival and Prices. The formula used for calculating the correlation (r_{xy}) is as follows.

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\text{Cov } x, y}{\sigma_x \sigma_y}$$

Where,
 r = correlation coefficient
 \bar{x} = Arrival Mean
 \bar{y} = Prices
 Cov(x,y) = Co-variance between x and y
 σ_x = standard deviation of x
 σ_y = standard deviation of y

Result and Discussion

Trend and Variation in Arrival and Prices of Onion.

Compound Growth Rate

From Table 1. The compound growth rates (CGR) for onion arrivals and prices show distinct trends across major markets. Pimpalgaon exhibits the highest positive growth in arrivals (1.26 per cent) and prices (0.52 per cent), both statistically significant at 1 per cent level. Lasalgaon and Bangalore also show significant price growth (0.47 per cent and 0.48 per cent, respectively), despite Bangalore's slight decline in arrivals. Pune's arrivals have a non-significant decline, but prices show significant positive growth (0.32 per cent) at 1 per cent level. Ahmedabad shows minimal changes in both arrivals and prices, with only price growth being statistically significant (0.27 per cent) at 5 per cent level.

Table .1 Compound growth rates in Arrival and Prices of Onion in five Major Markets in India.

	Arrival	Prices
Major markets	CGR (%)	CGR (%)
Lasalgaon	0.34**	0.47***
Pimpalgaon	1.26***	0.52***
Pune	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.32***
Bangalore	-0.13*	0.48***
Ahmedabad	0.01 ^{ns}	0.27**

(Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at 1, 5, and 10 percent respectively. ns indicates non-significance)

Coefficient of variation

Variability for Arrival of major markets of India were worked out for the period 2012 to 2022 shown in Table 2.
 The arrival of onions in the five major markets of Lasalgaon, Pimpalgaon, Pune, Bangalore, and Ahmedabad exhibited significant fluctuations. Lasalgaon market the maximum variability in arrival was observed in the year 2015 at 74.32 per cent, whereas the minimum variability in arrival was observed in year 2021 at 29.13 per cent. Pimpalgaon shows the maximum variability in arrival was observed in the year 2013 at 93.51 per cent and lowest was observed in the year of 2022 at 21.59 per cent. In the year of 2020 the Pune market shows the highest variability in arrival with 86.46 per cent and Lowest in the year of 2017 at 24.29 per cent. Bangalore shows its peak variability in the year of 2015 at 121.87 percent and lowest in 2020 at 12.76 per cent and the Ahmedabad market shows its highest variability in the year of 2020 at 41.33 per cent and lowest in the year of 2022 at 9.12 per cent. From the major markets the Bangalore market shows the highest variability in arrival was observed in 2015 at 121.87 per cent followed by Pimpalgaon, Pune, Lasalgaon, and Ahmedabad market. Whereas the lowest variability in arrival was observed in Ahmedabad market in the year of 2022 at 9.12 per cent followed by Bangalore, Pimpalgaon, Pune and Lasalgaon.

Variability for Prices of major markets of India were worked out for the period 2012 to 2022 shown in Table 3.

The fluctuations in onion prices across five major markets in India Lasalgaon, Pimpalgaon, Pune, Bangalore, and Ahmedabad from 2012 to 2022.

In Lasalgaon market the maximum variability in prices was observed in the year 2019 at 122.13 per cent, whereas the minimum variability in Prices was observed in year 2016 at 19.81 per cent. Pimpalgaon shows the maximum variability in prices was observed in the year 2019 at 129.91 per cent and lowest was observed in the year of 2014 at 15.07 per cent. In the year of 2013 the Pune market shows the highest variability in prices with 92.02 per cent and Lowest in the year of 2016 at 26.14 per cent. Bangalore shows its peak variability in the year of 2019 at 94.32 per cent and lowest in 2016 at 16.82 per cent and the Ahmedabad market shows its highest variability in prices in the year of 2019 at 79.13 per cent and lowest in the year of 2016 at 19.14 per cent. From the major markets the Pimpalgaon market shows the highest variability in prices was observed in 2019 at 129.91 per cent followed by Lasalgaon, Bangalore, Ahmedabad and Pune market. Whereas the lowest variability in prices was observed in Pimpalgaon market in the year of 2014 at 15.07 per cent followed by Bangalore, Ahmedabad, Lasalgaon and Pune.

Variability (CDVI) in Arrival and Prices of Onion in Major

Markets of India.

The variability of both arrival and prices of onion has been calculated using Cuddy Della Valle Index. The result is presented in Table 4. Variability in the market arrival is found highest in Bangalore market with an index of 53.48 per cent, while Ahmedabad market showed the lowest value index with 19.20 per cent. Variability in Prices was highest in Pimpalgaon market with an index of 61.11 per cent while lowest variability of prices showed in Bangalore market with an index of 48.79 per cent. It is found that Bangalore market is accounted for the highest variability in market arrival and for prices highest variability seen in Bangalore market. Also, Ahmedabad market is accounted for Lowest variability in market arrival and for prices Bangalore market.

Conclusion

The compound growth rates (CGR) for onion arrivals and prices show distinct trends across major markets. Pimpalgaon shows highest growth in both arrivals and prices, while Bangalore has a significant decline in arrival but strong price growth. Pune and Ahmedabad exhibit minimal changes in arrivals with moderate price growth. It shows significant price volatility across all markets, with the highest CV observed in Bangalore in 2015 and the lowest in Ahmedabad in 2022. Lasalgaon and Pimpalgaon experienced their highest CVs in 2015 and 2013, respectively, indicating notable price instability during those years. Pune and Bangalore had their lowest CVs in 2017 and 2020, respectively, suggesting more stable prices in those years. The data indicates significant price variability across all markets, with the highest volatility observed in 2019 and the lowest in 2016. Overall, price fluctuations are more pronounced in certain years, reflecting market instability and external factors influencing onion prices. The data shows that Lasalgaon and Pimpalgaon have the highest CDI for prices, indicating significant price growth. Ahmedabad has the lowest CDI for arrivals, suggesting minimal growth in market arrivals. The seasonal indices indicate that onion arrivals peak in January for most markets, while prices tend to be highest from August to November. This suggests a pattern where increased supply early in the year leads to lower prices, while reduced supply towards the end of the year drives prices up. The cyclical indices reveal a general decline in both arrivals and prices across all markets from 2012 to 2022. This trend suggests a consistent reduction in market activity over the years. However, Bangalore shows a notable increase in arrivals towards the end of the period, indicating a potential shift in market dynamics. Ahmedabad has a significant negative correlation between arrivals and prices, indicating that higher arrivals lead to lower prices. Other markets

exhibit non-significant correlations, suggesting no strong relationship between arrivals and prices.

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Table.4 CDVI of Onion Arrival and Prices in all Major Markets of India (2012-22)

Markets	Arrival	Prices
	CDVI (%)	CDVI (%)
Lasalgaon	50.76	59.40
Pimpalgaon	47.94	61.11
Pune	41.05	53.56
Bangalore	53.48	48.79
Ahmedabad	19.20	58.26

Table 7. Correlation Coefficient in Arrival and Prices of Onion in Major Markets of India (2012 to 2022)

Sr No	Markets	correlation	't' value
1	Lasalgaon	-0.26 ^{ns}	-0.81
2	Pimpalgaon	-0.31 ^{ns}	-0.97
3	Pune	-0.26 ^{ns}	-0.81
4	Bangalore	0.04 ^{ns}	0.13
5	Ahmedabad	-0.52 ^{**}	-1.84

11. (Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at 1, 5, and 10 percent respectively. ns indicates non-significance)

Table 2. Variability in Onion Arrival in Major Markets of India, (2012 to 2022)

Year	Lasalgaon		Pimpalgaon		Pune		Bangalore		Ahmedabad	
	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Qtl)	CV (%)						
2012	26994.07	33.73	14277.71	48.50	28671.08	37.33	53474.08	37.30	13149.88	11.72
2013	20384.58	68.37	10118.71	93.51	19125.53	70.21	63702.33	64.44	12551.00	31.09
2014	22203.52	55.39	16072.98	53.19	29635.48	51.34	75056.25	42.42	13460.18	15.87
2015	20544.83	74.32	29253.64	59.72	27903.31	40.37	115310	121.87	13645.23	22.46
2016	19616.00	68.70	27842.17	61.25	29307.33	30.07	76161.92	67.03	16754.17	11.58
2017	33189.58	54.54	44227.17	51.19	31816.00	24.29	52697.58	35.46	16724.44	16.05
2018	23874.00	49.69	33885.58	63.63	33988.75	42.64	66001	38.71	17554.63	9.78
2019	26788.58	55.52	36933.83	64.48	31079.75	24.64	57420.00	41.05	15968.99	17.50
2020	23573.08	70.15	36987.92	66.23	22323.75	86.46	50396.92	12.76	8994.86	41.33
2021	32431.25	29.13	40182.67	46.22	23920.75	31.70	50009.42	31.72	14677.61	39.19
2022	37753.50	32.38	43958.83	21.59	25282.25	33.17	52549.92	17.40	16813.68	9.12

Table 3. Variability in Onion Prices in Major Markets of India, (2012 to 2022)

Year	Lasalgaon		Pimpalgaon		Pune		Bangalore		Ahmedabad	
	Mean (Rs/Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs/Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs/Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs/Qtl)	CV (%)	Mean (Rs/Qtl)	CV (%)
2012	573.83	47.93	576.42	56.32	626.08	51.46	726.00	40.16	691.42	42.86
2013	2052.50	82.85	2271.18	87.24	1817.42	92.02	1742.00	45.98	2228.08	68.13
2014	1366.58	39.32	1447.56	15.07	1172.92	45.42	1283.17	37.23	1231.33	25.78
2015	2058.92	75.82	1940.83	85.54	2272.92	74.66	1745.92	41.80	1912.00	52.89
2016	772.92	19.81	666.83	20.43	872.50	26.14	730.50	16.82	710.83	19.14
2017	1260.08	79.15	1207.25	88.54	1226.50	71.97	1449.08	62.69	1321.17	76.74
2018	1092.58	51.65	1072.17	56.33	928.83	33.28	1155.33	52.60	1128.42	58.21
2019	2069.75	122.13	1987.33	129.91	1578.83	89.52	2262.25	94.32	1478.45	79.13
2020	1887.17	65.36	1888.42	73.36	1647.92	42.35	2029.50	61.17	2212.89	58.94
2021	1931.33	36.27	1958.83	39.67	1565.33	31.51	1920.67	34.45	1803.00	NA
2022	1476.83	32.94	1477.42	31.71	1218.92	27.10	1394.67	28.88	1388.00	32.91

Table 5. Seasonal indices of Arrival and Prices of Onion in Major Markets of India. (2012-2022)

States		Maharashtra						Karnataka		Gujarat	
Major Markets		Lasalgaon		Pimpalgaon		Pune		Bangalore		Ahmedabad	
Sr. No	Months	Arrivals	Prices								
1	January	159.99	105.14	102.74	100.55	147.56	98.18	147.86	104.25	102.52	113.29
2	February	131.31	89.58	93.37	90.09	160.88	81.87	85.64	91.73	107.11	90.15
3	March	75.55	60.46	59.21	57.27	155.31	58.50	85.94	65.03	111.11	72.62
4	April	76.39	51.79	122.64	52.40	97.04	54.61	74.82	55.35	107.64	57.03
5	May	129.65	56.10	175.81	55.04	87.07	57.44	72.61	57.22	118.80	53.41
6	June	129.93	75.51	139.79	71.66	70.12	78.08	66.71	76.48	101.18	71.73
7	July	118.39	85.58	118.31	82.75	76.28	90.50	62.64	89.18	96.42	85.31
8	August	104.75	123.75	106.16	117.18	71.87	126.08	74.62	106.27	80.57	125.68
9	September	74.94	133.13	93.10	135.35	65.93	134.28	116.33	113.68	84.15	134.31
10	October	53.89	147.44	58.61	156.67	77.32	141.41	176.31	134.81	97.15	147.31
11	November	32.14	143.16	37.98	152.49	82.24	152.32	138.40	151.84	100.82	143.54
12	December	113.05	128.34	92.29	128.54	108.38	126.73	98.13	154.16	92.53	105.63

Table 6. Cyclical indices for Arrival and Prices of Onion in Major Markets of India. (2012 to 2022)

Year	Lasalgaon		Pimpalgaon		Pune		Bangalore		Ahmedabad	
	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices	Arrival	Prices
2012	127.18	132.69	227.19	118.69	98.59	138.13	84.61	135.04	105.50	92.81
2013	120.63	124.55	181.12	114.41	98.87	128.34	87.30	126.19	104.35	94.16
2014	114.71	117.35	150.58	110.43	99.15	119.85	90.16	118.44	103.23	95.56
2015	109.35	110.93	128.86	106.72	99.43	112.41	93.22	111.58	102.13	96.99
2016	104.47	105.18	112.61	103.25	99.71	105.84	96.49	105.47	101.05	98.47
2017	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100	100	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
2018	95.90	95.30	89.93	96.95	100.29	94.77	103.78	95.07	98.97	101.57
2019	92.12	91.03	81.70	94.07	100.58	90.06	107.85	90.60	97.96	103.20
2020	88.63	87.12	74.86	91.37	100.87	85.79	112.25	86.53	96.97	104.88
2021	85.40	83.54	69.07	88.81	101.16	81.91	117.03	82.81	96.00	106.61
2022	82.39	80.23	64.11	86.39	101.45	78.37	122.23	79.40	95.05	108.40